

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 2 | APRIL - JUNE ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

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A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

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“NAVIGATING OUR WORKPLACE: THE ETHICAL WAY”

A leader is one who knows the way, goes the way, and shows the way.

-John C. Maxwell

As a college teacher I can attest to the need that the success of institutions primarily depends on effective leadership. John Maxwell posits “a leader is one who knows the way, goes the way, and shows the way” because they are the ones who will set the ethical standards employees should follow, vision on how our institutions will become in the long term, and provide stability in our organization. Thus, choosing the right leader is crucial. Yet, as Lacson (2014) asserts, that the “biggest obstacle” to our progress is our own leaders. I have been working for two academic institutions at the same time as a college instructor from my own experience and from what I’ve heard from my peers, social media, newspapers, and in television I affirm that our leaders are the cause of many problems in organizations across various industries. It may result from what Andres (1985) points out as a result of negative Filipino practices like the *lagay* or *pakikisama* system, where it’s not your credentials that matter but how much money you can pay to get the position. While others would resort to the *palakasan* system or the *padrino* system which is defined as a practice of gaining promotion or appointments through influential backers (Casauay, 2013). this resulted in incompetence and indecisiveness in important leadership decisions, corruption, and diminished work ethic.

Andres (1985) pointed out that Filipino family values tend to reflect attitudes in industry. He asserts these values: emotional closeness and security in the family, small group centeredness, authoritarianism, and personalism. Our administrators would always assert that we are a family. Our institution is our family. Also we tend to assert small group centeredness. Leaders tend to promote or reward individuals who come from his or her own group. Furthermore, we tend to like leaders who are authoritarian in nature. They should be firm to their decisions and would really assert to get the job done. It leads to many employees trying to get his or her favor. Finally, it’s always personal. There is a need to have a personal contact before things can happen. To say that “we are just doing our job and nothing personal” is a pretense. I see benefits in these values but we have to admit these are also hindrances to reform. In my experience it’s hard to correct or improve the system because constructive criticism might be seen as a personal attack. Knowing that we practice the *padrino* system and an assertion for small group centeredness you will have many enemies. Chances are you will be ganged up by the allies of the administrator or employee that you constructively criticize.

There is no perfect institution. Organizations would always have these kinds of issues as for me what I have to keep doing is to give my best in my profession. Possibly, if given a chance to have a leadership position I

will work for positive change in my institution. I attended a seminar conducted by the Center of Excellence in Learning, Teaching, and Assessment in Silliman University as one of the activities for the 117th Founder's Week Celebration. One of the speakers said: "We have a global problem. Yes we experience global warming but we are also experiencing global whining." We are challenged that instead of complaining we should do something to improve our institutions. What can we contribute for positive change? I can start by doing my work ethically. Uphold standards in my profession. If I would be given a chance to be in a leadership position I can learn insights from Andres (1985) which is able to achieve organizational goals using ethical management systems and the proper utilization of human resources and understand synergistic relationship between interpersonal competence, goals and systems.

REFERENCES

- Andres, T., (1985). Filipino Values and Productivity. Ch. 1 Pg. 5. The Role of Filipino Values in the Economic Development in the Philippines. Management by Filipino Values A Sequel to Understanding Filipino Values. New Day Publishers, Quezon City, Philippines.
- Andres, T., (1985). Filipino Attitudes and Values at Home and Industry. Ch. 3 Pg. 16. Management by Filipino Values A Sequel to Understanding Filipino Values. New Day Publishers, Quezon City, Philippines.
- Andres, T., (1985). Influences of Meaningful Goals in Organizations. Ch. 6 Pg. 31. Motivation of Individual Workers and Work Groups by Formal and Informal Organizations. Management by Filipino Values A Sequel to Understanding Filipino Values. New Day Publishers, Quezon City, Philippines.
- Casauay A., (2013). Santiago files bill vs 'padrino system'. Rappler. <https://www.rappler.com/nation/35581-santiago-senate-bill-padrino-system>
- Lacson, A., (2014). 'Our leaders, our problem'. Philippine Daily Inquirer. from <http://opinion.inquirer.net/75758/our-leaders-our-problem>
- Maxwell, J. C. (n.d.) Brainy Quote. Leadership Quotes. https://www.brainyquote.com/quotes/john_c_maxwell_383606?src=t_leadership